

WIND VALUE

An Opportunity for Climate Action and for Energy Communities

**End of Life Decisions for Wind Farms:
An Opportunity for Climate Action and for Energy Communities**

**Social Media and Website Setup
Deliverable 1.1**

Report on Month 2/48, April 2022

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Executive Summary

This research project seeks to estimate a financial valuation for onshore wind farms in Ireland. It will develop decision support tools which will assist wind farm managers to decide between decommissioning, repowering and life-extension for the end-of-life of a wind farm. This research will also assist local communities who may be interested in buying part or all of their local wind farm.

A social media channel, Twitter [@windvalue](#) and a website <https://windvalue.ie/> were set up during month 1 of the project (March 2022).

1 Report

The Twitter account, with handle [@windvalue](#) was set up during the first month of the project, March 2022. The website <https://windvalue.ie/> was also set up in March 2022. The passwords to operate these two sites have been shared with Peter Deeney and Dorcas Mikindani. The purposes of the project website and the Twitter account are to disseminate the output of the project and to facilitate engagement with stakeholders. In order to make the best use of these channels of communication both accounts were used to highlight topical news items and items of interest so as to attract interaction from stakeholders and the public.